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Detailed Specification of the Demonstrators

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.1 of the Shift2DC project presents the comprehensive technical specifications for five demonstrators that serve as practical implementations of Direct Current (DC) power technologies in varied application domains. These demonstrators aim to validate medium-voltage (MVDC) and low-voltage (LVDC) solutions under real-world conditions to advance the decarbonisation, resilience, and efficiency of future energy systems. This deliverable is foundational for the subsequent development, simulation, and evaluation activities within the Work Package 4 (WP4).

The document details each demonstrator's configuration, component specifications, single-line diagrams (SLD), Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and validation methodologies:

1. **DC Data Centres Demonstrator** (led by Fraunhofer IISB): Focused on edge data centres, this demonstrator showcases resilience and efficiency improvements using an integrated DC grid that powers both Information Technology (IT) and office areas. Key use cases include grid resilience, scalability, and sector coupling with Electric Vehicle (EV) charging and heat reuse.
2. **Services Building Demonstrator** (led by EDF): Implemented in a new office space, it evaluates the benefits of a 700V/350V DC grid for energy efficiency, self-consumption, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capability, and resilience. A full use case suite explores DC flexibility, Energy Management System (EMS) control, and protection strategies.
3. **Industrial LVDC Demonstrator** (led by Phoenix Contact): Located in the "AES Factory" in Germany, this demonstrator highlights modularity, scalability, and reliability of industrial DC grids. It integrates Photovoltaic (PV), Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), EV charging, and industrial processes, with use cases on protection systems, resilience, and sector coupling.
4. **LVDC/MVDC Operation and Protection Demonstrator** (led by EATON): This laboratory-scale demonstrator supports the analysis of meshed LVDC grids interfaced with MVDC systems. It enables testing of operational strategies, protection mechanisms, fault handling, and voltage stability using flexible converter setups.
5. **DC Port Digital Twin Demonstrator** (led by ITI/IST-ID): Combines a physical DC setup with a virtual digital twin to optimize port energy management, grid interaction, microgrid operations, and hydrogen integration. Four Business Use Cases cover operational scenarios from shore-side supply to port-wide energy hub functions.

The deliverable emphasizes the strategic alignment of these demonstrators with Europe's energy transition goals. It lays out a coherent methodology for verifying technical performance, economic viability, environmental impact, and system interoperability of DC-based technologies.

Together, these demonstrators establish a solid foundation for evaluating the Shift2DC innovations. This document will be succeeded by deliverables focusing on simulation results (D4.2), digital twin testing (D4.3), and lessons learned (D4.4), ensuring a systematic progression toward replicable and scalable DC deployments across sectors.

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
AFE	Active Front-End
AIC	Active Infeed Converter
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BMPU	Bidirectional Modular Power Unit
BUC	Business Use Case
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CB	Circuit Breaker
COS	Current/OS zoning philosophy
CPP	Critical Peak Pricing
CT	Current Transformers
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twin
EMS	Energy Management System
EMT	Electromagnetic Transients
ESS	Energy Storage System
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVSE	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
FEN	Flexible Electrical Networks
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Arrays
FRT	Fault Ride-Through
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
H ₂	Hydrogen
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HPC	High-Power Charging
HQ	Headquarters
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ILC	Interlink Converter
IoT	Internet of Things
ISOP	input series output-parallel
IT	Information Technology
ITW	Inter-tripping Wire
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LV	Light voltage
LVAC	Low Voltage Alternating Current
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
MAE	Mean Absolute Error

MCCB	Molded Case Circuit Breaker
MFT	Medium-Frequency Transformer
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
MV	Medium Voltage
MVAC	Medium Voltage Alternating Current
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
OCPD	Overcurrent Protection Device
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OPS	Onshore Power Supply
PDU	Power Distribution Unit
PGO	Port Grid Operator
PGS	Power Generation and Storage Systems
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RTP	Real Time Pricing
SECC	Supply Equipment Communication Controller
SELV	Safety Extra Low Voltage
SLD	Single Line Diagram
SO	System Operator
SOC	State of Charge
SOL	Shift2DC Solution Code
SPDU	Smart Power Distribution Unit
SSCB	Solid-State Circuit Braker
SSE	Shore Side Electricity
SSO	Shore Side Operator
SUC	Specialized Use Case
TN-S	Terre-Neutre Séparé (Earthing system)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
USB-C	Universal Serial Bus type-C
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The Shift2DC project follows the latest recommendation of the Strategic Energy Technology Plan [1], which promotes DC power distribution as the key technology for sustainable electrification. This project is dedicated to the development, testing, and validation of advanced MVDC and LVDC technologies across four key application domains: Data Centres, Services Building, Industrial Facilities, and Ports. This deliverable provides detailed specifications necessary for the establishment of practical demonstrators designed to validate these innovative DC solutions under realistic conditions.

The primary goal of Deliverable D4.1 is to precisely define each demonstrator's configuration, specify key technological components, and detail robust methodologies for their validation. This is accomplished by defining KPIs, ensuring thorough assessments of interoperability, scalability, security, economic viability, and environmental impacts.

This document covers the following demonstrators:

DC Data Centres Demonstrator: Validation of edge data centre approaches, resilience, and efficiency improvements through advanced DC infrastructure.

Services Building Demonstrator: Demonstration of DC integration in buildings to evaluate energy efficiency, self-consumption optimization, resilience, and flexibility through various DC-powered systems such as photovoltaics, storage, and electric vehicle charging.

LVDC Industry Demonstrator: Practical implementation and testing of DC infrastructure within an industrial environment, showcasing modularity, scalability, and robust protection systems.

LVDC/MVDC Operation and Protection Systems Demonstrator: Evaluation of the integration between low-voltage and medium-voltage DC grids, focusing on advanced operation, protection systems, and fault management strategies.

DC Port Digital Twin Demonstrator: Development and validation of a comprehensive digital twin representing DC infrastructure in maritime port environments, enabling optimized energy management, grid coordination, and microgrid integration.

1.2 Structure

The deliverable is structured to provide clear and systematic information, enhancing technical clarity and facilitating easy reference. Section 1 introduces the scope, objectives, and the overarching context of Deliverable D4.1. Sections 2 to 6 provide comprehensive specifications for each demonstrator, including detailed technical descriptions, infrastructure setups, defined KPIs, and validation methodologies. Section 7 highlights progress, identifies encountered challenges, and specifies future deliverables. This structured approach ensures that each demonstrator is thoroughly documented, allowing for systematic evaluation and verification during the implementation phase.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

This deliverable establishes a crucial foundation for the Shift2DC project implementation, underpinning subsequent phases and deliverables. It provides technical specifications that will inform future deliverables: **D4.2** Demonstrators' Simulation Results, **D4.3** Digital Twin Testing Environment, and **D4.4** Lessons Learned from Demonstrators. Each subsequent deliverable will expand upon the specifications, scenarios, and validation methods established here, ensuring coherent and continuous

project progression. Deliverables and milestones defined for all demonstrators in the WP4 are given in Table 1.1. They establish a WP4 implementation framework.

Table 1.1: Deliverable and Milestones with involvement of the Demonstrator

Deliverable/ Milestone	Project Month	Explanation
D4.1	M16	Detailed specification of the demonstrators
D4.2	M24	Demonstrators' simulation result
D4.3	M36	Digital twin testing environment
D4.4	M39	Lessons learned in Demonstrators
MS5	M30	Commissioning of the DC solutions in the demonstrators and creation of digital twins
MS6	M39	Conclusion of the validation phase of the demonstrators allowing the definition of a roadmap and guidelines for DC solutions

2 DC Data Centres Demonstrator

The DC Data Centre demonstrator is coordinated by Fraunhofer and will be implemented in the Bachmann facilities. The following sub-sections details the architecture and solutions that will be tested in DC Data centres.

2.1 Demo objectives, location, and time plan

Data Centres are an inherently DC based system and have been one of the main drivers behind early utilization of DC-grid power supply, due to efficiency gains when extending the (lead-acid battery based) in-line Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS). At the same time, the electrical infrastructure is highly hierarchical, which facilitates the design process. Nowadays, edge data centres are on the rise, and with it, the electrical infrastructure also needs to consider decentralized power sources, distributed sinks and sources and volatile prosumers. As such, the Shift2DC DC Data Centre Demonstrator will be set up to demonstrate an edge Data Centre approach supplied by a common DC power infrastructure.

In contrast to traditional co-location or hyperscale data centres, the end user and the computing power are spatially close to one another. This is also reflected in Shift2DC. The demonstrator will be set up in a container, which is divided into an office area and a data centre area, both supplied by the same DC-grid and utilizing waste heat from the data centre area within the office area. Resilience and reliability are paramount in the power supply of data centres. Therefore, the primary objective of the demonstrator is to showcase the inherent dependability of DC-based power infrastructure even under low-supply or fault situations.

The demonstrator will be set up in Germany at the premises of Bachmann GmbH (Ernstthaldenstr. 33, 70565 Stuttgart) as shown in Figure 2.1. A small container will be deployed in the parking space right outside the main building. It will include several solutions specifically developed within Shift2DC as well as commercially available components and systems. It could be mentioned that the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) standard for DC-grids within data centres is somewhat outdated as it does not consider edge data centres and distributed sources. As such, the demonstrator will follow the design and specification methodology of ODCA¹ and Current/OS².

¹ [ODCA](#)

² [Current/OS](#)

Figure 2.1 – Location of the DC Data Centre demonstrator at the premises of Bachmann GmbH in Stuttgart, Germany.

The participants have discussed the timetable both from a top-down and a bottom-up approach. In the first step, the overall project wide goals and demonstrator point of view were discussed, and a timetable was created. In a second step, the various timetables for the different solutions were compared with this and slight alterations implemented, where needed. The result is shown in Figure 2.2. Highlighted are the different deliverables and project wide milestones, which also mark specific milestones within the demonstrator.

	2024	2025												2026												2027		
	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	
	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	
4.1a	Specification				★																							
4.1b	Simulation												★															
4.1c	Installation																											
4.1d	Operation																											
4.1e	Analysis																											★

Figure 2.2 – Timetable for the Data Centre Demonstrator

2.2 Detailed single-line diagram

The grid topology of the data centre demonstrator is mostly based on the standard bus topology (Feed A). However, to account for edge data centre implementation approach, the battery system can be disconnected from the main busbar and utilized as a second – independent – feed for the server racks (Feed B). Both busbars are fed by droop-controlled power electronic converters, as such the grid voltage is variable with the nominal voltage area being 320 to 400 V. The bill of materials is presented in the Table 2.1.

Figure 2.3 – Single-Line Diagram (SLD) of Data Centre Demonstrator

Table 2.1: Bill of Materials

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Main parameters	Sourced from
High Power Density server rack	DC load	System max. power: 2 kW Standard power conversion, innovative servers and cooling solution	SOL9, SOL18
Partial Power Converter server rack	DC load	System max. power: 5kW Standard servers, innovative power conversion	SOL22, SOL15
Battery System	Prosumer	Capacity: 9.6 kWh Power: 4.8 kW Integrated DC/DC-converter	Procurement
Office Application and Lighting	DC load	Max. power: 1 kW It includes a workplace, presentation monitor and lighting, distribution on Safety Extra Low Voltage (SELV)-Level	SOL16
PV (MPPT)	DC source	Three panels on top of the container, each with a dedicated DC/DC-converter. Peak Power: 1,5 kW	SOL5
Active Infeed Converter (AIC)	DC source	Power: 30 kW Alternating Current (AC) side: three phase, 400 V	Procurement
Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE)	Prosumer	Power: 11/22 kW EV side voltage: Bidirectional System	SOL6
Switchgear and Safety Devices	Circuit protection	Exact dimensioning will be defined by protection concept, short-circuit and ground fault simulations. It will employ mixture of standard fuses, passive, hybrid and electronic circuit breakers.	Procurement (Use Shift2DC Solutions where possible)
Cables	Infrastructure	Copper diameter varies between 1.5mm ² to 25mm ²	SOL4

Two server racks will demonstrate the computing power, both with a different focus. On the one hand, **partial power converter rack** will be set up with standard servers, but the power supply will be realized with partial power converters specifically developed within Shift2DC (SOL22). On the other hand, the **high power density rack** will include specific server systems powered by SOL9 (Vertical Power delivery) and cooled by SOL18 (thermosyphon cooling system). The waste heat of this second rack can then be reused as a heating source within the office area of the demonstrator. Power Distribution within both server racks will be realized by SOL 15. The office area (SOL16) includes a full working place and lighting,

all powered by Feed A of the grid. PV panels will be set up on top of the demonstrator container and connected to Feed A with micro PV DC/DC-converters (SOL 5). Since the demonstrator will be located at the parking space of Bachmann, a DC powered EV charging system (EVSE, SOL6) will be connected to Feed A as well. A commercial battery system and an Active Infeed Converter (AIC) will be used to supply the grid. DC cables (SOL 4) will be used to connect the different sectors to the grid. For the infrastructure, like switchgear and protection devices, Shift2DC solutions will be utilized whenever possible, following the design of the protection concept and short circuit and ground fault simulations. The topology as well as power levels of the different sectors is depicted in Figure 2.3.

2.3 KPIs and their verification

Two sets of KPIs need to be examined: First are the KPIs of the different solutions that are set up within the container. Their target values and means of verification have been described in detail in WP1 (deliverable D1.4 [2]) .

The other set of KPIs pertains to the demonstrator itself and stems mostly from the actual operation of the DC grid. The system level KPIs are listed in Table 2.2. For power measurements (current and voltage), the internal measurements of the various converters will be utilized to realize *a)* a higher resolution in the time domain, and *b)* reduce the costs of material and installation overhead.

Table 2.2: KPIs on Demonstrator level for Data Centre Demonstrator

KPI	Description	Means of Measurement
Uptime	Availability of Data Centre	Server logs
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness from Sink to Source	Measurement of voltage and current in all supply sectors, as well as server load logs
Uptime in Island Mode	Server Uptime, when disconnected from the AC-Grid	Server logs and power measurement in AIC-sector
Reuse of waste heat power	Percentage of waste heat power that can be reused within the office area.	Measurements within cooling system
Self-consumption	Percentage of locally generated energy (via PV) that is consumed by the computing systems in comparison to the amount that is fed back into the AC mains.	Power measurement in multiple sectors (PV, battery, servers, AIC)

2.4 Use cases to be tested

In deliverable D1.3 [3], various Use Cases (UC) have been described in detail and published in a database.

This work has been approached from the perspective of the demonstrators, focusing on three core use cases for the Data Centre Demonstrator:

- UC DCe1 – DC grid resilience
- UC DCe2 – Data centre scalability
- UC DCe3 – Sector coupling

In **UC DCe1**, the primary focus is to ensure the continuous availability and reliability of the computing units. The edge approach brings computing power closer to applications and data sources, thereby reducing latency and enabling real-time applications. However, the local power infrastructure is not always optimally developed to support this. Various scenarios, such as AC grid failures or defects in different converters, are defined within the use case description and will be implemented during the demonstrator operation to test the resilience of the DC grid.

UC DCe2 emphasizes the scalability of both computing power and electrical capacity. The edge approach necessitates a flexible and modular network that can adapt to changes in local conditions. Unlike traditional data centres, this use case aims to implement and test a software-based adjustment of computing power according to the available electrical capacity.

The third use-case, **UC DCe3**, demonstrates the potential of sector coupling. Utilizing server waste heat in the office area of the demonstrator, along with (bidirectional) coupling with the mobility sector, presents a flexibility potential that cannot be realized in conventional data centres. Particularly in conjunction with UC DCe1, the coupling of electric vehicle charging facilities on a direct current basis offers significant potential.

For further information on those Use Cases and scenarios, their implementation and operation, refer to D1.3 (the database of use cases) [3].

3 DC Distribution in Services Building Demonstrator

The Building demonstrator is coordinated by EDF and will be implemented in the Cegelec Nord Tertiaire facilities. The following solutions will be provided by the different participants:

- Converters:
 - Interlink Converter (ILC): Schneider (SCHND) / DC Systems (DCS),
 - DC/DC converter, Power Distribution Unit (PDU): Watt & Well (W&W),
- Protection systems: Schneider (SCHND) / DC Systems (DCS),
- Bidirectional EV Charging station: Watt & Well (W&W),
- PV integration (FlexiVerter): TalTech (TALT),
- DC Cables: Nexans (NEXNS),
- EMS: Eaton (EATCZ).
- Communication Gateway: CIRCE

3.1 Demo objectives, location, and time plan

Objectives

The main objectives of this demo are listed below:

- Implementation: Implement, install, and test the Shift2DC project's solutions.
- Field: Evaluate the feasibility of a DC Building infrastructure and capitalize on field feedback.
- Assessment: Evaluate the expected benefits of DC integration into commercial and residential buildings:
 - Energy efficiency compared to a conventional AC building,
 - CO₂ footprint reduction compared to a conventional AC building,
 - Operational Expenditure (OPEX) & Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) analysis compared to a conventional AC building,
 - Self-consumption enhancement and flexibility of the demand/production of the installation,
 - Resilience capabilities in case of asset loss.
- Experimental: Perform and test the DC Office Building use cases:
 - Flexibility resulting from droop control capabilities,
 - V2G & Services for AC main grid,
 - Self-consumption enhancement,
 - Resilience.

Location

The demonstrator will be implemented as an extension of existing offices (140 m²) of Cegelec Nord Tertiaire at 31 Rue Pasteur, 59290 Wasquehal FRANCE (in northern France, see Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 – Building demo location

Time plan

The timeline of building demonstrator was aligned with Cegelec considering the procurement and certification requirements. Considering that will be a building used for regular operation and used as workspace, all the standards and rules must be guaranteed according to the Frech directives. Detailed planning is presented in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 – Building demo timeline

3.2 Detailed single-line diagram and/or general structure

3.2.1 Single-line diagram

The demo will be powered by an ILC of 50/60 kW. It will be supplied by the AC grid (3-phase 400 V_{AC}, 50 Hz) and it will provide a unipolar 700 V_{DC} bus.

The 700 V_{DC} bus will interconnect:

- A battery storage system of 10 kWh with a nominal power of 8 kW³,
- A PV system:
 - o Around 60 kWp: PV panels on the roof and converters in the technical room (ground),
 - o 4 kWp: 10 FlexiVerters directly connected to 10 units of 400Wp PV panels on the roof,
- 2 EV chargers: 11 kW each with V2G capabilities for one unit.
- 700 V_{DC} loads like DC fed heat pump, if available.
- The PDU provides 350 V_{DC} bus.

Unidirectional PDU (11 kW in this case) will power 350 V_{DC} bus. This bus will provide energy to office loads, such as lights, computers, printers through small converters to have the appropriate voltage (under 20 V for computers and printer, above 48 V for lighting, etc.). 350 V_{DC} bus will also provide energy for other loads like kitchen appliances, such as a DC fed fridge. The final definition of the DC loads is still in decision process.

Preliminary single-line diagrams are available on Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4 (General architecture and preliminary electrical SLD). A more detailed preliminary single-line diagram is available on [APPENDIX A: Building Demo – Detailed single-line diagrams](#).

Figure 3.3 – Building demo general architecture

³ Battery system capacity and power are indicative. The exact values will depend on the procurement.

Figure 3.4 – Building demo preliminary electrical single-line diagram

3.2.2 Bill of materials

The bill of materials and the descriptions are based on the current available information. Considering that the procurement phase is not finalized, the following information is subject to minor changes. The bill of materials is presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Building demo – bill of materials and description

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Participant	Sourced from
Energy Router ⁴ (Conv_1)	Interlink converter – Bidirectional interface between LVAC and LVDC networks with droop power voltage control functions Power: 100 kW Voltage: 700 V	Schneider / DC Systems	SOL7
Storage System (Conv_2)	Preliminary sizing: 8kW/10kWh	Procurement	To be defined
EV Charging Unit 1 (Conv_3)	Power: 11 kW; Operating Voltage: 700 V. Current/OS compliant.	Procurement	To be defined
EV Charging Unit 2 (Conv_4)	High Density Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) DC station for high efficiency energy exchange. Power: 11 kW; Operating Voltage: 700 V. Current/OS compliant.	WATT & WELL	SOL6
FlexiVerters (Conv_5, Conv_6, Conv_11, Conv_12, Conv_13)	Micro Solar DC Systems – FlexiVerter® technology for PV systems integration is a universal software-defined DC/DC converter with advanced control functions optimizing the PV generation/storage units.	TALTECH	SOL5
Other electronic devices – Computers – Lighting (Conv_7, Conv_8, Conv_9)	DC/DC converters or AC/DC converters compatible with DC input. 350 V to 48 V (the device will have an internal converter or will be powered with a socket like Universal Serial Bus Type-C (USB-C) with integrated 48 V converter to USB-C voltages).	Procurement	To be defined
PDU (Conv_10)	Smart Power Distribution Unit is a DC/DC isolated converter that converts 700 V to 350V and allows the PDU to control the energy flow between power sources and loads. Power 11 kW; Current/OS compliant.	WATT & WELL	SOL14
DC Cables	Smart and sustainable DC cables – Cable system optimized for DC applications	Nexans	SOL4
EMS	EMS tool for AC/DC Hybrid Systems the management and control.	EATON	SOL21
Communication Gateway	A communication gateway as interface between EMS and devices/assets	CIRCE	
Static protection System	Protections systems to limit risks of overcurrent, electric shocks, overvoltage thermal effects and arcs, adapted to DC grids.	Schneider / DC Systems	SOL8

⁴ This solution is not funded as prototype by the Project and will be submitted to a parallel commercial transaction between Schneider / DC Systems and Cegelec Nord Tertiaire.

3.3 Preliminary system sizing

The preliminary system sizing was made based on the preliminary single-line diagram (Figure 3.4) with the tool developed in T2.1 [1]. The input parameters are presented in Table 3.2.

Sizing scenarios

The sizing is based on two operating scenarios considered as potential worst cases:

- In the first, the AC contribution is set at 100%, the PV contribution is set at 0%, the storage contribution is set at -100% to force the batterie to act as a load and the load consumption is set at 100%.
- In the second one, the AC contribution is set at 0%, the PV contribution is set at 100%, the storage contribution is set at -100% to force the batterie to act as a load and the load consumption is set at 100%.

Installation conditions

Cables are considered installed in protective cabling tubes in non-buried dedicated cable trays. Following International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 60364-5-52 standard philosophy, an installation reduction factor named K for cabling tubes is applied. This reduction factor corresponds to:

- $K = 0.61$ for the worst installation case with a number of 3 circuits joined on a cable tray with an ambient temperature of 30 °C⁵.
- $K = 0.87$ for the worst installation case with a unique circuit on a cable tray with an ambient temperature of 30 °C⁶.

This factor is applied to the nominal current $Current_{Nominal}$ passing through the grid (calculated based on the scenarios above) to determine the minimal ampacity of the cable and its cross section ($Ampacity_{min} = \frac{Current_{Nominal}}{K}$).

In the T2.1 tool [1], a cable sizing factor α is used for all the cables. A conversion between α and K is necessary, following the formula below:

$$K = 100 * (1 - \frac{\alpha}{100})$$

In our case: $\alpha = 13\%$ for the links between Active Front-End (AFE) – 700V busbars and 700V busbars – PV busbars, and $\alpha = 39\%$ for all other circuits.

Table 3.2: Input parameters for the building demo sizing

Ecosystem	Current/OS	Poles	Unipolar
Total PV (kWp)	64	Number of PV converters	5
Number of DC voltage level	3	Number of AC/DC converters	1
Total EV (kW)	22	Number of EV DC/DC converters	2
Number of storage DC/DC converters	1	Total storage capacity (kWh)	8
Total storage power (kW)	10	Number of PDU DC/DC	4
Operating temperature (°C)	30	Material of the conductors	Copper
Isolation of the conductors	XLPE	Cable sizing factor α (%)	39*

*Installation reduction factor of 0.61 according to IEC 60364-5-52, see details above.

⁵ Following IEC 60364-5-52 ($K_1 = 0,87, K_2 = 0,7, K_3 = 1 \rightarrow K = 0,609$)

⁶ Following IEC 60364-5-52 ($K_1 = 0,87, K_2 = 1, K_3 = 1 \rightarrow K = 0,87$)

Figure 3.5 illustrates the result of the sizing tool in form of a single-line diagram. Lines are shown in red, while nodes are marked in blue. Converters are represented by black bold lines.

Figure 3.5 – Building demo preliminary sizing

The detailed results of the sizing are given in Table 3.3. The preliminary sizing gives lower cross sections values compared to usual cross sections in AC systems.

Table 3.3: Results of the building demo sizing

Line	From node i	To node j	Cross Section (mm ²)	Power (kW)
AFE to Busbars 700 V	1	2	25	60
Busbars 700 V to Storage	2	4	1	8
Busbars 700 V to EV1	2	6	2.5	11
Busbars 700 V to EV2	2	8	2.5	11
Busbars 700 V to PV Busbars	2	11	25	60
PV converters to PV panels 1	22	9	2.5**	12
PV converters to PV panels 2	23	10	2.5**	12
PV converters to PV panels 3	25	24	2.5**	12
PV converters to PV panels 4	27	26	2.5**	12
PV converters to PV panels 5	29	28	2.5**	12
PV Busbars to Flexinverters	11	30	1	4
Busbars 700 V to SPDU	2	19	2.5	11
SPDU to Computers	18	13	1	0.5
SPDU to Lighting	18	15	1	0.5
SPDU to Electronic Devices	18	17	1	0.5
SPDU to 350V Load	18	20	1.5	1
Busbars 700 V to 700 V Load	2	21	6	10

** It should be noted that the cable cross sections are standardized for the lines between the PV panels and the converters, the minimal cross section is 4 mm². The design tool does not take this standard into account. It will also depend on the association in series/parallel of PV module and the resulting voltage of the lines between PVs and converters.

3.4 Protection plan

The protection plan section is divided into two sub-parts. First, the demonstrator is divided into protection zones according to the Current/OS system reference document [4]. Second, based on preliminary studies, the protection equipment is selected.

3.4.1 Protection zones

The zoning depends on the type of protection used: semiconductors (SSCB) or fuse/ Molded Case Circuit Breaker (MCCB). At this stage, due to the limited Solid-State Circuit Braker (SSCB) catalog on the market, the possible range of breaking capacity of SSCBs is not well defined. As a precaution, only SSCBs rated for a line current of 16 A have been considered. Therefore, zoning is done in with:

- SSCB to protect circuits with a current under 16 A (11 kW on 700 V),
- Fuses to protect circuits with a current higher than 16 A.

Even in Current/OS zoning philosophy (COS) zone 1, some devices need to be protected by fuses, such as batteries or PV strings.

Figure 3.6 – Building demo preliminary zoning with hybrid system protection

Zone 0:

The DC side of the AC/DC converter, the battery and the bus side of the battery converter are in **Zone 0** because they are non-protected high-power voltages sources (with large capacitors for the converters). Here, when power is higher than 10 kW, we assume that there are large capacitors. To avoid being Zone 0, the capacitors energy needs to be lower than 600 J. This means the overall capacitance capable to contribute to a fault does not exceed 2.3 mF in 700 V_{DC} systems, or 9 mF in 350 V_{DC} systems.

Zone 1:

The connections between the battery and the battery converter, the 700 V_{DC} busbars and its connections to the battery converter, to the output of the AC/DC converter and to the PV converters are in **Zone 1**, because these links are fed by high-power sources, and they are protected by a passive protection (fuse).

Zone 2.1:

The 350 V_{DC} busbars, the outputs of 48 V_{DC} converters, 48 V_{DC} loads, and the links between PV strings and their interface converters are in **Zone 2.1** because in this zone the current is limited by converters (PV haven't unlimited power and we assume that 48 V loads converters are current limiting).

Zone 3:

The EV2 is in **Zone 3** because it's a bidirectional converter with low fault energy protected by fast OCPD. This line has multiple sources. The EV1 is in **Zone 3** because, even if it is a unidirectional converter (and protected by OCPD), it is not clear if it has an input diode.

Zone 4:

The line for the Smart Power Distribution Unit (SPDU) converters, circuits for 350 V loads and the line for the heat pump are in **Zone 4** because they are fed by a single source and protected by fast OCPD, ensuring very low fault current and energy (devices also have input diodes).

Important remarks:

- The battery fuse needs to be near the battery.
- If the link between the battery and its converter is longer than a specific distance (approx. 10 m); it is needed to have a fuse at each end of the link.
- The PV panels will be organized in series/parallel association, and they may have a collector box on the roof near the panels. A fuse is needed at the output of the roof collector boxes to protect the links between roof collector boxes and the PV converters.
- In these diagrams, the inter-tripping wire (ITW) is not represented.

3.4.2 Protection preliminary sizing

Based on maximum load capacities and available protection device on the market, a preliminary sizing is provided below. Following the methodology currently under development in the project⁷, a complementary Electromagnetic Transients (EMT) simulation is needed to confirm or adjust these protection devices rates.

The preliminary protection sizing is given in Table 3.4. Voltages reference are the minimum voltages of the system (640V and 320V).

⁷ Will be provided in deliverable D2.2 of SHIFT2DC Project.

Table 3.4: Building demo protection sizing – hybrid protection system

Fuse	P (kW)	U (V)	I (A)	gPV*	gR*	SSCB	P (kW)	U (V)	I (A)
Fuse_1	60	640	93.8	100	100	SSCB_1	11	640	17.2
Fuse_2	8	640	12.5	15	16	SSCB_2	8	640	12.5
Fuse_3	8	**	**	**	**	SSCB_3	11	640	17.2
Fuse_4	12	640	18.8	20	20	SSCB_4	10	640	15.7
Fuse_5	12	640	18.8	20	20	SSCB_5	11	640	17.2
Fuse_6	12	640	18.8	20	20	SSCB_6	1	320	3.2
Fuse_7	12	640	18.8	20	20	SSCB_7	0,5	320	1,6
Fuse_8	12	640	18.8	20	20	SSCB_8	0,5	320	1,6
Fuse_9	4	640	6.25	8	8	SSCB_9	0,5	320	1,6
Fuse_10	60	640	93.8	100	100				

* gPV and gR refer to photovoltaic and semiconductor fuses, respectively, both with full-range breaking capacity.

** For this sizing, the battery voltage needs to be defined explicitly (after procurement).

3.5 KPIs and their verification

The KPIs for the building demo are presented in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5: KPIs on Demonstrator level for Building Demonstrator

KPI	Description	Means of Measurement
KPI1 Resilience	The AC grid supply is interrupted for different operating points, DC demo shall remain operational.	Time of operation disconnected from the AC grid
KPI2 Self-consumption	DC demo optimizes its operation to reduce energy consumption from the main AC grid while maintaining (defined) essential loads	Relation between the power consumed from PV and the total consumption
KPI3 Self-consumption time	For a defined duration, DC demo would operate in high proportion from local resources supply.	Time with zero consumption from the grid
KPI4 Energy efficiency field calculation	Validate theoretical assumptions regarding energy efficiency for a DC commercial building compared to a reference case of an AC building	Relation between power losses using DC infrastructure and AC one (Theoretical)
KPI5 Flexibility capabilities	Measure energy resources flexibility including DC loads, electric vehicles with Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) capability and storage systems. PV shedding can also be used as flexibility	Relation between baseline power demand and power demand after flexibility services activation

KPI6 Device outages and power quality	Appliances outages due to power quality issues (under or overvoltages, sags, etc).	Time of outage per device.
KPI7 User Experience	Survey the user experience related with DC devices and the use of the installation	Qualitative analysis using user survey
KPI8 Operation and Maintenance (O&M) technician experience feedback	O&M technician provides feedback regarding the DC demo O&M (e.g. safety instruction and indications), considering technologies Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs).	Interview the technicians collecting feedback related with the installation and maintenance of DC equipment/devices.

3.6 Use Cases to be tested

Five UC will be considered in the building demonstrator:

- **UC Bld1 – DC grid resilience**

- **UC Bld1.1 – DC microgrid islanding operation**

One of the main features explored here is the capability of a DC grid to operate independently from the upstream AC supply grid. This use case considers relying on local generation and storage units and control strategies, with the disconnection and reconnection to the grid happening seamlessly without interruption. Such features limit the impact of AC grid faults on the DC microgrid, allowing a higher availability.

- **UC Bld1.2 – EMS droop curve change function of operation mode**

The aim is to prove the DC system capability to dynamically swap from one operating mode to another relying on the EMS to detect changes in the operating conditions and to activate the most relevant control strategy (droop curve change among others). As an example, in case a major source is faulty, droop curves are automatically adapted by the EMS to reduce power consumption and re-allocate load sharing between the remaining sources ensuring grid stability.

- **UC Bld2 – DC grid self-healing and flexibility management**

- **UC Bld2.1 – Load Flexibility**

The aim will be to ensure that the loads, such as EV charger, can adapt their power following the droop voltage curve, in accordance with COS standard. For example, if the bus voltage is high, the EV charger can switch to fast charging mode (increase the charging power). In contrary, if the bus voltage is low, the EV charger would switch to a slow charging mode by decreasing or interrupting the power consumption level.

- **UC Bld2.2 – V2G Capabilities**

The aim will be to ensure that the EV charger reacts to the induced voltage reduction and switches from sink mode to source mode, in case of very low local resources production or a faulty asset.

- **UC Bld3 – DC energy hub**

This use-case intends to mitigate the building impact on the AC grid by taking advantage of all DC flexibilities to optimize self-consumption using multi-level optimization strategies allowing better energy sharing. Such concepts are key to facilitate the integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DER), when compared to AC grid alternatives, and adapt consumption to local production.

The aim will be to prove that DC demo has a low consumption from AC grid in case of high price signal for example. DC system would rely mainly on local resources and DC flexibilities to optimize balance between consumption and production. Dynamic changes in droop voltage configurations and asset prioritization are key to achieving this feature.

- **UC Bld4 – DC services to the AC grid**

Flexibility services provided to the AC grid will also be explored to evaluate the adaptability of the DC system to situations of high and low power availability (for voltage/frequency control). The two major local constraints for a Distribution System Operator (DSO) are:

- Local congestion due to low power availability: In this case, the DC system would, if technically feasible, decrease or interrupt power consumption from AC grid during a certain period of time. Ideally, this service is pre-defined (range of power consumption reduction and duration) and triggered by an external signal to the DC system.
- High voltage due to high power availability locally: In this case, the DC system would, if technically feasible, decrease or interrupt power injection to the main grid by curtailing local power production or increasing power consumption of flexible loads as EVs or storage. Ideally, this service is pre-defined (range of power injection reduction and duration) and triggered by an external signal to the DC system or AC grid voltage.

Notice: This use case requires a bidirectional AFE converter with capability to receive operating setpoints.

4 LVDC industry demonstrator

The industrial demonstrator is led by Phoenix Contact, which will also host the demonstrator at its headquarters factory in Blomberg, Germany.

4.1 Demo objectives, location, and time plan

Industry is one of the major consumers of electricity in industrial countries. Depending on the products that are being manufactured, the individual industrial processes differ a lot regarding their power demands. The range is from instantaneous power demand of a rather static level up to very discontinuous power peaks. Industrial production typically involves many electric motor drives. Since many years, those drives are equipped with inverters to efficiently and accurately control the motor speed. Each of the power electronic based inverters is equipped with a DC intermediate circuit which motivates the use of DC supply. With the powerful power electronic devices available nowadays, there is nearly no application left where it is required to still run an AC grid, although there are countless individual appliances and processes. It is evident that this variety leads to the requirement to set up industrial DC grids in a flexible way, to match each characteristic, each device and each process.

Another characteristic of industrial grids is the strict requirement of high reliability and availability of the electrical power supply. Thus, robustness of the DC grid is core for usage in industrial environments. The manufacturing building not only comprises the manufacturing processes but also some other typical building appliances such as lighting, heating, ventilation, air conditioning (HVAC), building automation up to PV system and EVSE integration. Therefore, the demonstrator will include these appliances and show their interaction within the DC system since they all are suitable to be supplied with DC. Some of these applications are quite similar to general commercial building but in combination with the industrial manufacturing processes they have their own individual characteristics and requirements.

4.1.1 Location

In the Industrial DC Demonstrator, the LVDC Part will be implemented at the Headquarters (HQ) of Phoenix Contact, Blomberg, Germany (Figure 4.1). This demonstrator is following the concept of the ODCA focusing on industrial DC grids and providing a system specification for design and operation of such. This specification is also available as VDE Spec 90037⁸.

⁸ VDE Spec 90037, system design specification available at www.vde.com

Figure 4.1 - Location of the Industrial DC Demonstrator of the LVDC Part at Phoenix Contact HQ, Blomberg

A brand-new building called “AES factory” (Figure 4.2) was recently established at the HQ of Phoenix Contact in Blomberg, Germany. Parts of the building including production are to be set up with a DC grid to demonstrate the reliability and availability of a DC power supply. Since several DC assets such as a PV system, batteries, 10 DC high power charging (HPC) units and peripheral equipment and building technology is connected beyond an exemplary production unit itself, this allows to execute various tests within this multi-source DC system.

Figure 4.2 - Building "AES Factory" comprising the LVDC Industrial DC Grid demonstrator

Phoenix Contact plans to operate and show this industrial DC demonstrator for the purpose of the Shift2DC project and also for future demonstration to visitors of the company and offer tours for delegations to promote DC technology.

4.1.2 Roadmap

The roadmap of the Industrial LVDC demonstrator is independent of the Industrial demonstrator site of EATON/RWTH Aachen, focusing on MVDC-LVDC interface. Thus, the individual roadmap is planned as shown in Figure 4.3. Since there are many dependencies on the entire building commissioning and extended DC grid, slightly changes may happen; however, there is confidence to match the planned schedule.

Figure 4.3 - Roadmap of the industrial LVDC demonstrator - Phoenix Contact, Blomberg

4.2 Detailed single-line diagram and/or general structure

The single-line diagram of the Industrial DC demonstrator depicted in Figure 4.4 comprises several assets which are not linked to production itself. However, an industrial production building typically addresses peripheral assets which are certainly necessary in many types of buildings. Especially when it comes to sustainable power supply, rooftop PV systems are often involved nowadays. Furthermore, batteries are also often found in such systems. Considering that many of the consumers also operate directly from DC, adding new consumers, such as DC charging, DC grid makes a great deal of sense and increases efficiency.

A bus structure was identified to match best the requirements. It collects power input from a few individual DC sources beyond the central AIC, supplying the DC bus with a nominal voltage of 650 V DC while being supplied by a conventional 400 V AC feeder at the primary side. In the first phase synchronized with the Shift2DC demonstrator goals, the DC bus has rather short lines. The DC system is characterized by multiple DC sources which can concurrently feed the DC bus. In the final stage all DC chargers will be equipped with bidirectional charging capability, thus 10 more DC supply units can feed back DC power to the bus. Providing grid services to the AC grid is also possible since the AIC employs a bidirectional design.

Figure 4.4 – SLD Industrial LVDC Grid Demonstrator

Table 4.1 shows the main components which are part of the solutions and latest developments needed to investigate the use cases planned within the Shift2DC project.

Table 4.1: Bill of Materials

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Main parameters	Sourced from
19" BESS	A modular and scalable concept of a 19" rack mounted BESS with high flexibility in stabilizing the DC grid voltage. Both power as well as energy modules are designed to allow quick exchange to support high reliability and availability in Industrial DC grids.	30-1000 V DC Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) input	SOL19
DC Measurement Device	The proposed solution will provide a wide range measurement up to 1000 A DC and 1500 V DC to support all DC grid operation schemes possible within the LVDC domain. A digital interface will provide the essential measurement data to DC grid controllers	1000 A 1500 V 1% accuracy	SOL12
DC Connector System	To distribute DC power safely a DC system approach with a junction box with an active hybrid connector technology to prevent arcing is established and used to connect devices.	Arc free connector 800V 20A	SOL20
DC Circuit Breakers	A hybrid DC circuit breaker with internal pre-charging function of the connected application and comprehensive protection functions is used to connect some of the assets to the Industrial DC grid, where appropriate in terms of specification	Pre-charging short circuit protection remote switching 800V 55A	Self-developed

4.3 KPIs and their verification

Phoenix Contact is working on three important solutions within the Shift2DC research project to establish and operate DC grids and attached devices and applications safely and reliably. The following overview depicts the KPIs proposed for this demo considering the solutions that will be tested in the demonstrator. The most important KPIs of this demonstrator are presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: KPIs on Demonstrator level for Building Demonstrator

KPI	Description	Means of Measurement
KPI1 Measurement Devices	Validate the accuracy of measurement devices	Compare measurements of current and voltage obtained in the demonstrator (SOL12) with reference values. The error should be lower than 1%.
KPI2 Efficiency of BESS participating in flexibility services	Evaluate the efficiency of the BESS when used in different types of flexibility services.	Comparison between the energy used to charge the BESS (SOL19) and the one obtained in the discharge. The target is to guarantee a global efficiency higher than 90% and higher than 96% in the power module.
KPI3 Comparison between passive and active DC connectors (number of connections)	Evaluate the number of connections allowed by different types of connectors	Number of cycles (Connection / Disconnection)
KPI3 Comparison between passive and active DC connectors (Voltage/Current)	Evaluate the maximum voltage and current allowed for each type of connector	Maximum Voltage and Current
KPI4 Voltage Droop control accuracy	Evaluate the accuracy of voltage droop control	Compare the theoretical voltage droop control with the measured one
KPI5 Resilience of DC system	Evaluate the performance of the system in extreme operation conditions (overvoltage, undervoltage, sag, etc)	Outage time.
KPI6 Self-consumption	DC demo optimizes its operation to reduce energy consumption from the main AC grid while maintaining (defined) essential loads	Relation between the power consumed from PV and the total consumption

4.4 Use Cases to be tested

Operators of industrial production facilities and process plants require a high availability of power and reliable supply. Outages, which pause or stop production processes, can result in significant costs. Nowadays, energy prices and sustainability goals such as decarbonization are very much the focus of facility management and energy managers. For electricity, peak power management and prevention have become a business case on its own. All these goals can be achieved at the same time by optimizing the grid operation and managing the connected assets by an appropriate EMS, though still giving the production the highest priority. Flexibility of the connected assets is key. Where immanent system flexibility is insufficient, additional BESS can add the flexibility required to achieve the goals.

Use Case: Operation of an Industrial LVDC Grid

The Industrial demonstrator at Phoenix Contact site, concentrates on the high-level use case of operation of an industrial DC grid to supply industrial applications, such as production machines but also comprises the facility part with its applications and devices. To prove the reliability of such DC powered distributions, the central use case of this demonstrator focuses on significant scenarios, typically found in similar setups, such as:

- Switching on the DC grid
- Grid and devices pre-charging
- Intrinsic voltage support by individual converters
- BESS balancing of the nominal voltage band
- Outage prevention by combination of multiple sources
- Shutdown of the DC grid

The use cases that will be evaluated are the following ones:

- **UC1: DC System resilience**
The aim is to evaluate the performance of the system under various operating conditions, including voltage variations, short circuits, and voltage fluctuations. The BESS will play a key role in addressing these issues. However, an evaluation of the contribution of each device is also expected to be performed.
- **UC2: DC protection system**
This use case will focus on the evaluation of two main aspects. First, the protection system will be tested under different types of events, such as overcurrents and short circuits. These tests will also enable the assessment of protections' selectivity. The second aspect to be tested is the performance of the active and passive connectors.
- **UC3: Flexibility, modularity, scalability**
The main aim of this use case will focus on evaluating the system's performance under different topologies. While the main topology will remain unchanged, the use of active and passive connectors enables the integration of various devices at different points in the system and allows adjustment of the power supplied. This evaluation will provide insights into the behavior of the overall system in the context of modular and scalable architectures.
- **UC4: Sector coupling**
This use case aims to evaluate the overall performance of the DC system when integrated with the industrial process. Two key elements will be monitored: the behavior of the EMS and the use of the BESS to coordinate and compensate for the needs of the industrial process, support self-consumption of energy production, and optimize energy costs.

While this demonstration site focuses on the LVDC part only based on a busbar grid type, the industrial demonstrator at RWTH Aachen site (ch.5) investigates the meshed network grid type and its operation and includes the MVDC level. Furthermore, it focuses on investigation aspects like protection, fault identification and isolation.

5 LVDC/MVDC operation and protection systems demonstrator

The LVDC/MVDC demonstrator is a joint effort between RWTH Aachen University and EATON, and forms part of RWTH Aachen Living Lab within the Shift2DC project. Given its scale and system capacity, the demo is positioned as a supporting element to the Industrial Demo activities and serves for the preliminary evaluation of operational and protection strategies and components.

The infrastructure is being developed and expanded by the Institute for Power Generation and Storage Systems (PGS) at the E.ON Energy Research Center of RWTH Aachen University. Components for protection, efficient operation, as well as operational strategies and the protection plan are being developed by EATON and integrated into the demonstrator. Nexans will provide the smart DC cable solution for the setup. The testing and demonstration of various aspects of a meshed LVDC network will be carried out collaboratively by RWTH Aachen University and EATON.

5.1 Demo objectives, location, and time plan

In future industrial environments, DC distribution networks are expected to interconnect various infrastructures, including buildings, industrial facilities, and manufacturing plants. These installations typically have power demands in the range of several hundred kilowatts, comparable to the supply capacity of conventional low-voltage AC (LVAC) distribution transformers. Larger facilities with higher power requirements, or significant generation units such as utility-scale photovoltaic (PV) parks, present strong potential for integration via MVDC lines. These lines enable efficient and controllable power transmission over longer distances. Nonetheless, energy consumption and local integration generally take place within a LVDC network. Compared to traditional radial AC distribution systems, meshed LVDC grids offer advantages in terms of supply reliability and overall system resilience.

To explore these benefits, RWTH Aachen University and EATON are developing a demonstrator to investigate the operation and protection of meshed LVDC networks, including their integration into MVDC systems. This demonstrator is a joint effort between RWTH Aachen University and EATON and is located at the E.ON Energy Research Center on the Melaten Campus (Figure 5.1). It builds upon the existing MVDC research infrastructure established under the Flexible Electrical Networks (FEN) research campus initiative. Figure 5.2 provides a top view of the new LVDC installation. The current MVDC system is being upgraded and expanded through the integration of this LVDC setup. The operation scenarios will be defined by EATON emulating real operation conditions of EATON factories.

As part of the installation, a new grid connection point and a containerized infrastructure platform are being constructed. These are connected to the MVDC test hall via underground cable ducts. The overall system is designed to enable detailed investigations into the operation and protection of meshed LVDC networks and to demonstrate their seamless integration into higher-level MVDC systems. Consequently, the demonstrator forms a central element of the RWTH Living Lab within the framework of the Shift2DC project. The modular LVDC grid topology and integrated components allow for a flexible configuration that can be adapted to suit different demonstration and research objectives.

Figure 5.1: Demo site at RWTH – Aachen University at Campus Melaten

Figure 5.2: Demo site at RWTH – Top view of the new LVDC installation

Main Objectives:

- Demonstrate the real-scale operation of meshed LVDC networks
- Demonstrate and evaluate secondary and tertiary control strategies
- Assess and validate protection plans for LVDC and MVDC systems

To achieve these objectives, the demonstrator—and the broader Living Lab environment—will be continuously expanded over the course of the project. This phased development ensures that individual components can be tested within a system-level context. The goal is to progressively increase the TRL of each solution and ultimately demonstrate the functionality of the overall system.

Deployment and Commissioning Plan:

Infrastructure preparation and construction work are already underway and will be completed by Q3 2025 (Figure 5.3). Starting in September 2025, the converters and smart DC cable will be installed, followed by the protection and control systems in Q4 2025 and Q1 2026. As the demonstrator is part of the Living Lab initiative, continuous 24/7 operation is not feasible after commissioning. Instead, during the operational and monitoring phase, a series of experiments and sub-demonstrations will be conducted to validate different use cases and system configurations.

		13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41
		Dez	Jan	Feb	Mrz	Apr	Mai	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Okt	Nov	Dez	Jan	Feb	Mrz	Apr	Mai	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Okt	Nov	Dez	Jan	Feb	Mrz	Apr
WP4	DC Solutions: Demonstration and Field-tests																													
T4.3 a	Design and Specification																													
T4.3 b	T4.3b – DC Industry Demo – Operation simulation																													
T4.3 c	Installation and Commissioning																													
T4.3 d	Operation and Monitoring																													
T4.3 e	Analysis of Results																													

Figure 5.3: Time plan.

5.2 Detailed single-line diagram and/or general structure

The final configuration of the demonstrator/Living Lab is shown in Figure 5.4, which is designed to address the defined use cases. To achieve this goal, the demonstrator will not be built in its final form from the outset. Instead, it will be developed iteratively, allowing for the step-by-step evaluation of individual sub-goals. The bill of materials is presented in Table 5.1.

The sub-goals include:

- Operation of the meshed LVDC grid controlled by the EATON EMS
- Control of power flow within the meshed network using droop characteristics implemented via the EMS
- Integration of visualization and control of circuit breakers (CBs)
- Integration and operation of LV/MV DC converters within the newly constructed LVDC network
- Fault handling and evaluation of fault ride-through (FRT) behavior in the MVDC network
- Integration and routine operation of circuit breakers within the demonstration grid
- Verification of selectivity through active disconnection of specific line segments
- Testing of selectivity and performance of the LVDC circuit breakers by inducing controlled short-circuit events within the LVDC grid

Figure 5.4: SLD Industrial MVDC/LVDC Grid Demonstrator

All converters in the SLD are isolated from the surrounding AC and MVDC grid. The isolation is achieved either via a galvanically isolated DC-DC converter using a medium-frequency transformer (MFT) or by a line-frequency isolation transformer at the ac stage, where the star point is not grounded. This flexible setup allows the demonstration system to apply and evaluate different earthing configurations, such as IT or *Terre-Neutre Séparé* (TN-S) system. Furthermore, configurations with and without a DC midpoint can be implemented as some converters are capable of mid-point voltage-balancing. Initially the system will be configured as a TN-S system without a mid-point.

Table 5.1: Bill of Materials

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Main parameters	Sourced from
MVDC/LVDC Converter	Bidirectional interface between the MVDC and LVDC grid. This component will participate in the active dc-droop voltage regulation.	High-Side Voltage: 5000 V Low-Side Voltage: 400 V - 900 V LVDC Capacitor: 4- 32 mF per Pole (400 V) Power: 75 – 320 kW	RWTH
Active Infeed Converter (AIC) (3L)	Bidirectional interface between the LVAC and LVDC grid. This component will participate in the active dc-droop voltage regulation. Additional power set-points to receive or inject active power the ac grid are considered.	LVDC Voltage: 600 V – 800 V DC-Link Capacitor: 2x2mF Power: 50 kW	RWTH
Isolated Active Infeed Converter	Bidirectional interface between LVAC and LVDC grid. Two-Stage Converter with Medium-Frequency Isolation Stage with FRT capability. This component will mimic the behavior of a downstream dc-grid. It will act as source/load according to artificial setpoints derived from a downstream grid.	LVDC Voltage: 600 V – 820 V DC-Link Capacitor 4.3 mF Power: 150 kW	RWTH
Battery Energy Storage System (BESS)	DC-coupled storage with droop control. This component will participate in the active dc-droop voltage regulation.	Power: 40 kW, Energy: 20 kWh	EATON
Flexible Load	Bidirectional electronic Load to emulate the behavior of additional loads/sources in the grid that are user controlled.	Power: 15-30 kW Voltage: 600 V - 800 V	RWTH
Load	Resistive load bank to apply load steps used for testing of dynamic voltage stability.	Power up to 300 kW for 10 s	RWTH

DC Cables	Smart and sustainable DC cables – 120 mm ²	Conductor cross-section: 120mm ² R' = 250 mOhm/km L' 220uH/km Unom = 750 V	Nexans (SOL 4)
EMS / DC-Grid Controller	A central DC grid controller with Human Machine Interface (HMI) and EMS functionalities.		EATON (SOL 21)
Short Circuit Generator	A device capable of creating artificial short circuits with the positive and negative rail of the dc cable.		RWTH
Circuit Breaker	Semiconductor based fast acting circuit breaker.	40-100 A 800 V (2P, 1P+M) Target tripping: 5-10 us	EATON (SOL 10)
Pre-Charging Unit	A pre charging unit within the CB to allow connection of devices with reduced inrush currents and power up of grid segments.		EATON (SOL 11)

5.3 KPIs and their verification

The Demo/LivingLab provides a testing environment for evaluating various solutions implemented within the LVDC and MVDC grids. It supports the assessment of KPIs related to the following components:

- SOL 10 – Semiconductor-Based Circuit Breaker
- SOL 11 – Pre-Charging Unit
- SOL 17 – Voltage Sharing Control
- SOL 23 – White EMS

The subsequent objective of the Demo/LivingLab is to test protection strategies and to ensure the resilient and stable operation of the LVDC/MVDC grid. It is important to note that the Demo/Living Lab is not intended for continuous operation. As such, the evaluations conducted do not target long-term operational goals. Instead, the focus is on short-term functional validation and system response under predefined test scenarios.

The system level KPI evaluation activities are summarized in the Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: System-Level KPIs

KPI	Description	Means of Measurement
Grid Voltage-Stability	The LVDC grid is objected to sudden changes in either load/source or sudden changes in the network due to faults or reconfigurations. The operable voltage band should not be exceeded	Distributed voltage measurement.
Grid Resilience	The DC grid is objected to sudden changes in either load/source or sudden changes on the LV or MV network due to faults or reconfigurations. The system should stay operational and manage the power flow automatically.	Distributed voltage and current measurement at the LV and MV side. Voltage and Current Measurements on the devices captured using the HMI of SOL23.
Fault-detection and fault isolation time	After a short circuit is induced in the grid, the time to fault-detection and fault-isolation on a system level is measured and compared.	Distributed Voltage and Current Measurement within the LVDC set-up.
Inrush Current Limitation	The power-up of the LVDC grid segments will be sequentially carried out by the pre-charging unit minimizing the inrush current of the individual grid components.	Current and Voltage Measurement at the DC-link of the individual components.

5.4 Use Cases to be tested

The demo is intended to apply the following Use Cases:

- UC6: Operation of LVDC grids
- UC7: Interfacing LVDC a meshed and MVDC grids
- UC5: Fault detection and isolation in a meshed LVDC grid

UC5: Fault detection and isolation in a meshed LVDC grid

This use case aims to operate an industrial meshed LVDC grid with DC protection technology. The scenarios are intended to demonstrate the process of pre-charging individual components and grid segments, normal operation, as well as the detection and interruption of fault currents, and the isolation of the faulty section. Different grid architectures, ranging from radial to mesh (ring) systems, will be implemented. The protection of the converters will be carried out using DC circuit breakers (SOL 10) and fault-tolerant converter topologies (SOL 26). Different fault scenarios will be emulated, and the process of fault detection, clearing, isolation, and reconfiguration - along with the resulting power flow adjustments- will be tested. Additionally, different circuit breaker technologies will be employed and evaluated for their suitability in the respective protection functions.

UC6: Operation of meshed LVDC grids

A meshed LVDC grid enhances system reliability by ensuring that critical processes and systems are continuously supplied with electrical energy. For example, local LVDC grids within buildings or production facilities on industrial sites can be integrated into a meshed DC grid structure. This

configuration allows critical loads to be supplied via multiple grid segments, ensuring continued operation in the event of a segment failure. A meshed or ring bus DC grid with several feed-in points from higher-level power grids can achieve high availability and distribute the required peak power to several grid connections. Superimposed grids for integration can be classic AC grids as well as medium-voltage DC grids. The use case scenarios comprise the black start of the grid, the normal operation with AC grid coupling, the peak power reduction of individual grid connection points and the maximization of the self-consumption within the meshed dc grid.

UC7: Interfacing LVDC and MVDC grids

A meshed LVDC system consisting of multiple converters and loads, will be interfaced to an MVDC system by an MV to LV converter. Bidirectional power transfer between both systems will be assessed. Cables of different lengths interconnect the LVDC components. Different potential placements of LVDC protection equipment will be evaluated and compared to assess the impact of faults on the meshed system.

6 DC port digital twin demonstrator

The port digital demonstration is being developed at the Port of Funchal, hosted by APRAM (Administração dos Portos da Região Autónoma da Madeira). This initiative, led by the Interactive Technologies Institute (ITI) from IST-ID, brings together a diverse consortium of partners across research, port operations, utilities, and technology development.

The demonstration follows a digital twin (DT) approach, combining a physical and a virtual component to enable real-time monitoring, control, and experimentation. On the physical side, a set of DC infrastructure elements is being deployed on-site to serve as a reference implementation, grounding the model in real operational constraints. The virtual layer will simulate and extend this physical setup, allowing for dynamic scenario testing, predictive control, and system optimization. This hybrid setup ensures that the demonstration remains closely tied to the reality of port operations, while enabling flexibility and foresight in planning future energy transitions.

6.1 Demo objectives, location, and time plan

The maritime sector is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, responsible for about 2.5% of the total. Reducing emissions from this sector is thus necessary to address climate change. This is further supported the International Maritime Organization's decarbonization goals, highlighting the need for cleaner and more efficient solutions [5].

One of the most promising ways to lower emissions is through electrification. This includes using technologies like batteries, hybrid systems, and shore-side electricity (also known as cold ironing), which allow ships to rely less on fossil fuels and operate more efficiently [6].

DC technologies are increasingly seen as an enabler for this transition. Many modern energy systems—including batteries, solar photovoltaics, and electric propulsion—operate natively on DC. By adopting DC infrastructure, ports can reduce energy conversion losses, improve efficiency, and simplify the integration of renewable sources and storage. A further advantage lies in avoiding frequency compatibility issues common in AC systems, where ships and ports may operate at different standards (50 Hz vs. 60 Hz), requiring costly and inefficient frequency converters. In contrast, DC systems bypass this problem entirely, offering a universal interface that can be adapted onboard [7].

Demo objectives

Considering these emerging trends and challenges, this work aims to investigate the implications of integrating DC into port energy systems by focusing on four main objectives.

- To assess the impact of integrating DC either in a hybrid or full DC setup, in port operations, efficiency and infrastructure.
- To understand how ports can support sustainable and seamless grid integration by facilitating smoother energy flows between local systems and the broad electrical grid.
- To explore the feasibility of operating ports as resilient and autonomous microgrids by leveraging local generation, storage, and smart management systems in microgrid configurations.
- To investigate the role of ports as energy hubs for multi-energy integration and grid support, considering multiple energy vectors (e.g., electricity, hydrogen, and storage).

Location

The port demonstration is being developed at the Port of Funchal. The demonstration will take place in the port area primarily dedicated to cruise ship operations, which can accommodate two large cruise ships simultaneously and is also the docking location for the ferry boat connecting Madeira to Porto Santo Island. This area houses all the necessary facilities to support maritime operations, as well as most of the offices for port-related activities. Figure 6.1 depicts the demo location in Madeira Island (left) and in the Funchal Port (right).

Figure 6.1: Port digital twin demonstrator location: in Madeira Island (left), in the Funchal Port (right).

All necessary technologies for the demonstration will be installed in this same area, near the main electric switchboard for this specific port zone, ensuring efficient integration with the existing electrical infrastructure. An overview of the area mentioned is presented in Figure 6.2, including an approximate location of the assets that will be deployed.

Figure 6.2: Overview of the specific demo area and planned location for the demonstration equipment to be deployed.

Time Plan

The demonstration activities are divided into four main subtasks, as depicted in Figure 6.3: *i)* design and specification, *ii)* monitoring system installation, *iii)* development of the digital twin simulation platform, and *iv)* analysis of the results.

Figure 6.3: Port digital twin demonstration time plan.

The **first subtask**, ending at the end of M17 (Abril 2025), corresponds to this deliverable and included all the activities related to the definition of the demonstration activities. During this phase, the demonstrator areas were selected as shown in Figure 6.2, the single-line diagrams were created and the necessary equipment (e.g., cables and converters) were selected and procured – more details about these steps are provided in the following sections.

The **second subtask**, started in M16 and will last until M21 (August 2025), corresponds to the installation of the hardware and software infrastructures that will support the demonstration activities. At this stage, an energy monitoring system was installed to measure the electricity consumption in the areas where the demonstration activities will run. Besides the total demand, submetering is being performed for 32 three phase partial boards. For illustration purposes, Figure 6.4 shows one day of total active power demand in the monitored area.

Figure 6.4: Representation of one day of active power demand in the monitored area of the Funchal Port.

The next steps involve the installation of the 10 kWp PV system, and of the different solutions that will comprise the physical part of the demo. A comprehensive list of the different solutions to install in the Port of Funchal is provided in Table 6.2.

The **third subtask** will start in M18 and will last until M38 (February 2027), and it comprises all the activities related to the development of the digital twin and the implementation of the four case studies. These activities include: *i)* development of the communication and control layer of the hardware assets, *ii)* development of the power flow simulation, *iii)* development of the EMS and integration with the communication and control layer, *iv)* development of the visualization layer.

The **fourth subtask** will start in M27 and will last until M39 (March 2027), comprising the activities related to running and evaluating the different demonstration use cases. Each use case will be developed considering three setups of the power system: i) full DC, ii) hybrid AC-DC, where only the Renewable Energy Sources (RES), EVs and Onshore Power Supply (OPS) related operations will be in DC, and iii) full AC, which will be the baseline scenario.

6.2 Detailed single-line diagram and/or general structure

To better understand the interaction between existing port infrastructure and the planned DC integration, this section starts by presenting a high-level overview of the demonstration setup. The diagram in Figure 6.5 distinguishes the physical and virtual components that will constitute the Port digital twin. On the one hand, the top two layers show the physical components: the existing AC infrastructure that will be modelled in DC – *“Existing Port Grid”*, and the DC infrastructure that will be installed – *“Physical Demonstrator”*. On the other hand, the bottom two layers show the purely virtual components: the infrastructure to simulate an Energy Hub – *“Port Energy Hub”*, and the infrastructure to simulate the provision of Shore Side electricity to the vessels – *“Shore Side Electricity”*.

Figure 6.5: Diagram illustrating the relationship between the AC and DC components of the demonstration setup.

It is important to highlight that the existing port grid will be modelled as a DC system, but it will be dynamically powered by real measurements collected through the port’s energy monitoring infrastructure. Additionally, the "Physical Demonstrator" layer features two key interfaces: a **Digital Twin Interface**, which links the physical demonstrator to the fully simulated DC grid of the Port for virtual experimentation, and an **Operational Grid Interface**, which enables the physical connection of the DC assets to the existing AC Port infrastructure for real-world validation and testing.

The "Physical Demonstrator" will be installed in the locations shown in Figure 6.1 where a Current/OS compliant grid, operating at 350 V_{DC}, will be deployed with the following assets:

- A 11 kW ILC, C1, interfacing with the existing AC grid.
- A PV system with 10 kWp on the roof that interfaces the DC grid via an 11 kW DC-DC converter in the technical room, C5.
- A 10 kWh BESS that interfaces the DC grid via a bidirectional 11 kW DC-DC converter in the technical room, C3.
- A 22kW EVSE (composed by two bidirectional 11 kW DC-DC converters) installed in the parking lot, C6.
- A 11 kW DC-DC converter that will interface a variable load that can be used to emulate seaport operation assets (lighting, cranes, etc.), based on realistic profiles that will be generated through data-driven processes. This will be installed in the technical room, C4.
- A 3 kW DC-AC converter that will be used to power a forklift charger, to be installed outside the technical room, C6.

The preliminary single line diagram of the hardware infrastructure that will be deployed in the Port is presented in Figure 6.6, highlighting the locations of the components – either in the private technical area or external, i.e., publicly accessible.

Figure 6.6: Detailed SLD of the Physical Demonstrator (to be installed).

The port energy hub intends to explore the possibility of operating high-power levels of renewable energy to leverage and optimize the usage of high interconnect power required for the shore side supply to accommodate cruise ships. The power levels are yet to be defined as different scenarios will be studied in the DT tool. The renewable energy resources models will be data-driven models.

The shore side electricity (SSE) component of the demo explores the possibility to operate 3 10MW DC/AC converters operating in MV to meet the demand requirements of 3 berth stations each capable to accommodate a 10MW cruise ship.

Table 6.1 shows the preliminary sizing for the DC cables. L33 to L41 refers to the lines that will be installed in the physical demo and required an early definition, while the remaining lines can be changed at any time in the DT tool. The length of the cables is already estimated but the final values will be determined during the installation phase. However, for the existing installation the lengths will be estimated based on the existing information (not accurate) and on the comparison of the theoretical values of the voltages and currents and the measurements. This method allows a better characterization of the real installation.

Table 6.1 Results of the port demo DC sizing for normal feeding system.

Lines	DC Sized Cross Section (mm ²)	Length (m)	Power (kW)	Lines	DC Sized Cross Section (mm ²)	Length (m)	Power (kW)
L1	185(x3)	TBD	620	L25	4	TBD	22
L2	2.5	TBD	16.5	L26	6	TBD	30
L3	10	TBD	40	L27	6	TBD	30
L4	1.5	TBD	3	L28	6	TBD	32.2
L5	1.5	TBD	9	L29	35	TBD	92.5
L6	2.5	TBD	15	L30	4	TBD	23.1
L7	1.5	TBD	11.5	L31	4	TBD	24.5
L8	25	TBD	67.5	L32	35	TBD	80
L9	1.5	TBD	11.5	L33	10	<10	11
L10	2.5	TBD	18.5	L34	10	<10	11
L11	2.5	TBD	18	L35	10	<10	11
L12	10	TBD	42.5	L36	10	<10	11
L13	1.5	TBD	12.5	L37	10	30	11
L14	35	TBD	90	L38	10	30	11
L15	185 (x2)	TBD	500	L39	10	<10	22
L16	240	TBD	305	L40	10	<10	11
L17	1.5	TBD	10	L41	10	20	10
L18	16	TBD	50	L42	TBD	TBD	TBD
L19	1.5	TBD	8.5	L43	TBD	TBD	TBD
L20	10	TBD	45.5	L44	TBD	TBD	TBD
L21	1.5	TBD	7.5	L45	TBD	TBD	TBD
L22	1.5	TBD	7	L46	TBD	TBD	10000
L23	1.5	TBD	8.5	L47	TBD	TBD	10000
L24	10	TBD	45	L48	TBD	TBD	10000

Table 6.2 shows the main components which are part of the solutions and latest developments in order investigate the use cases planned within the Shift2DC research project.

Table 6.2: Port Digital Twin Demonstrator Bill of Materials.

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Main parameters	Sourced from
Smart Metering and Edge/Cloud Computing			
eGauge Pro	CT meter that can measure the power of individual circuits in an electric panel using sensors called current transformers (CTs).	Measures electric AC or DC power on up to 30 circuits; 2 USB Inputs; DC Voltage port; Ethernet Communication; For residential, commercial, municipal, and industrial use; BACnet IP and MS/TP compatible; Modbus TCP and RTU communication; FCC and UL-61010 compliant;	Procurement
Strato Pi UPS Server	Industrial grade Raspberry Pi, designed to act as a server	UPS; RS-232 and RS-485 interfaces; RTC, watchdog and secure element; CE/FCC/IC compliant.	Procurement
RevPi 5	Industrial grade Raspberry Pi, designed to act as an edge-device	Quad-core ARM Cortex-A76 processor at 2.4 GHz; Two PCIe-based Gigabit Ethernet ports with low latency	CIRCE
PV and BESS			
Solar PV Installation	PV panels and supporting equipment	23 x RUNERGY HY - DH108N8 435W BF for a total of 10 kWp	Procurement
BESS	Modular rack-mounted Li-Ion BESS	10 kWh BESS comprised of 5 rack mounted batteries with 2kWh each.	Procurement
Others / Miscellaneous			
Equipment Cabinet	19' cabinet to accommodate the BESS and converters	22U height cabinet	Procurement
DC Cables	Smart and sustainable DC cables	10mm ² , copper with intertripping wire.	Nexans (SOL 4)
EVI	Supply Equipment Communication Controller (SECC)	Compliant with IEC 61851-23 and IEC 61851-1 requirements subset for SECC, and with IEC 61557-8 and UL 2231-1/-2 standards for IMD. EVI can act as a main controller of an EVSE and is compatible with BMPU	W&W
Converters (DC-DC AC-DC DC-AC)			
DC – DC Converter	BMPU-R2-DC is a specific configuration, compatible with DC grids. Typical application: electric vehicle supply	Grid Input 500V – 32A; EV Side 500V – 32A	W&W

Device/piece of equipment	Type	Main parameters	Sourced from
	equipment (EVSE) connected to ESS or DC grid		
AC Grid Connection	Grid-tied power supply capable of bidirectional conversion between AC (grid) and DC.	11 kVA Bidirectional Power Unit, 4-phases; AC connection to standard 400/480 VAC, 50/60 Hz grid. No neutral required; DC Side 500V – 32A	W&W
Protections			
Protections	Converter protection: Upstream MCCB: EDGEDC3040FFG (x6) 3-Pole; 500 Vdc; In=40A Downstream MCB: FAZ-C13/2DC (x6) 2-Pole; 500 Vdc; In=13A PV surge protection: SPPVRT2-600-2+PE (x1) 3-Pole; 600 Vdc.	The downstream allows for a current of 26A during about one hour and will cut-off a current of 95A within 10ms, thus protecting the current converter equipment. The upstream will protect from short-circuit currents with expected peaks of about 3 kA within cut-off times of about 50 ms. PV surge protection from currents up to 20 kA within 8-20 microseconds.	Eaton
Tools			
EMS	Centralized Energy Management System	Open-source EMS allowing the management and control of the physical and virtual DC assets.	ITI, INESC-ID, NEW (Custom)
DC Power Flow	DC solution design tool	Update version of the tool to support the online and real-time simulations required by the Port Digital Twin	EDF/CIRCE (SOL 23)

6.2.1 Shift2DC Solutions and Technologies

Several Shift2DC solutions will be tested in this demo, including business models, technologies and tools.

Business Models:

- **SOL2: Participation in grid and system services** – three of the four Business Use Cases (BUC) consider the participation of the port in grid services – BUC2, BUC3 and BUC4. Several business models will be considered, including implicit and explicit demand response (DR), and frequency regulation. BUC3 will also consider the possibility of microgrid islanding, while BUC4 will consider the possibility of using also hydrogen (H₂) to support the Port operations.
- **SOL3: Energy hubs management** – in BUC4, new business models will be proposed considering the possibility of generating H₂ on site and using it to generate electricity. Other business models will explore the possibility of selling H₂, either directly to the vessel operators (as an alternative fuel), or to local retailers.

Technologies:

- SOL4: Smart and sustainable DC cables – 100 meters of smart and sustainable DC cable will be used in the Port demo. The used cable will be unipolar with intercropping wire, and a cross-section of 10mm². The voltage level considered will be 350 V_{DC} for the main DC bus. The cable samples will be supplied by Nexans
- BMPU-R2-DC DC-DC Converter – a 11 kW DC-DC Converter typically used for EVSE and Energy Storage Systems (ESS). This solution will be supplied by Watt&Well, and will be coupled with the 10 kWp PV system, the 10 kWh BESS, and the 11 kW EVSE.
- Bidirectional Power Unit – R (BMPU-R) – a 11 kVA bidirectional converter between AC (grid) and DC. This solution will be supplied by Watt&Well, and will be the connection point between the Port’s AC grid and the Shift2DC demo DC grid.
- EVI-C2-O SECC – a Supply Equipment Communications Controller that can act as the main controller for an EVSE. It is compatible with BMPU. It will be supplied by Watt&Well and coupled with one of the BMPU-R2-DC DC-DC Converters to form the 11 kW EVSE that will be tested in the demo.

Tools:

- SOL21: EMS tool for AC/DC hybrid systems – a custom EMS will be developed for the Port demo. Whenever possible, modules from SOL21 will be adapted – in particular, the modules that enable direct control of the physical assets through the Circe Internet-of-things (IoT) device.
- SOL23: DC solutions design tool – a DC power flow simulator based on SOL23 will be incorporated in the Port DT. The key change that will be performed is enabling real-time simulations by promoting communication using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) objects.
- SOL24: DC solutions simulation tool using digital twins – several DC solutions will be modeled in the DT both in hardware and software. For example, DC-DC converts will be emulated using Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), whereas vessel charging profiles will be generated using generative AI methods, leveraging real-world profiles provided Fincantieri SI.

6.3 KPIs and their verification

Several KPIs will be developed and evaluated in the DC Port Digital Twin demonstration. The KPIs have been grouped based on four themes: *i*) energy performance and efficiency (Table 6.3), *ii*) machine-learning performance (Table 6.4), *iii*) economic and costs factors (Table 6.5), and *iv*) flexibility and demand response (Table 6.6). These KPIs will be implemented and assessed in each of the use case scenarios presented in this Section. A mapping between the KPIs and the use cases is presented in Section 6.4.5.

Table 6.3: KPIs for Port Energy Performance and Efficiency

KPI	Name	Description
KPI1	Peak Consumption	Measures the maximum peak in power measured at the Port.
KPI2	Ramping Factor	Measures the maximum delta in power between two consecutive intervals.
KPI3	Self-Consumption	Measures of how much of the energy produced at the Port, e.g., from PV or H ₂ , was consumed onsite.
KPI4	Self-Sufficiency	Measures how much of the energy consumed at the Port was produced locally. E.g., from PV or H ₂ .
KPI5	Power Curtailment Needs	Measures the amount of power that needed to be curtailed in the Port. It can be calculated for different periods.

KPI6	Shore Side Battery Use	Measures the use of the batteries that are installed in the Port. Several values can be obtained, including charge/discharge cycles and the average State of Charge (SOC).
KPI7	Vessel Battery Use	Similar to KPI6 but measures the batteries in the vessels.
KPI8	Voltage Deviation	Measures the difference between the nominal voltage and the measured voltage. Can be in percentage or absolute value.
KPI9	Accuracy in Frequency Regulation	Measures how accurately the system responds to frequency regulation requests. It is given by the ratio of the measured and theoretical power responses.
KPI10	Load Power Factor	Measures the quality of the power in terms of power factor.
KPI11	H ₂ Production	Measures the amount of H ₂ that was produced onsite
KPI12	H ₂ Storage Efficiency	Measures the efficiency of storing H ₂ on site.
KPI13	Connections Rejected	Measures the number of vessel shore connections that must be rejected. Rejections can occur due to system incompatibility (not possible to measure in the project), or unavailability of OPS equipment for another vessel.

Table 6.4: KPIs for Learning Algorithms

KPI	Name	Description
KPI14	Forecasting Error	Measures the relation between forecasted values and measured values. Can be applied for the different resources - Consumption, Production, Ship Power Profile. Different metrics can be considered like Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) or Mean Absolute Error (MAE).
KPI15	Forecasting Divergence	Measures the difference between two forecasts of the same resource. E.g., vessel operator vs. the Port Grid Operator (PGO) forecasts of power demand. It can be measured in several ways, e.g., the delta of the individual forecast errors, or a forecasting error metric calculated on top of the two predictions.

Table 6.5: KPIs for Economic and Cost-related Factors

KPI	Name	Description
KPI16	Daily Operations Costs	Measures the costs of operating the port. It can be calculated using different target. E.g., Total Euros, Euros per kWh.
KPI17	Use of Peak Power Cost	Measures the costs incurred due to the use of peak power.
KPI19	Load Factor cost	Relation between the peak and off-peak cost
KPI19	Operation Cost Divergence	Measures the difference in costs of two different modes of Port operation. E.g., Real-Time Pricing vs. Flat Rate. It can be measures in different ways, e.g., a delta or the ratio between the two costs.
KPI20	Cost Savings	Measures the savings that the port incurred by reducing the costs of port operation.
KPI21	Incentives Received	Quantities the total amount of incentives received for participating in the grid services.
KPI22	Energy Selling Profits	Measures the profits of selling energy to the grid

KPI23	Energy Selling to EVs	Measures the profits of selling energy to EVs
KPI24	H ₂ Profits	Measures the profits of operating H ₂ generation facilities onsite.

Table 6.6: KPIs for Flexibility and Demand Response

KPI	Name	Description
KPI25	Flexibility Participation Index	Measures the different in flexible power between the requested and the executed.
KPI26	Time Participation Success Rate	Measures the amount of time that the service was not provided. It can be given by the ratio between the time below the expected and the total expected time.
KPI27	Power Participation Success Rate	Measures the ratio between the flexible power measured and what was expected, i.e., the power setpoint.
KPI28	Time of Participation	Measures the amount of time that the service was provided as requested. It can be calculated as the ratio between the time of participation and the expected participation time.
KPI29	Power consumption Reduction	Measures the amount of power consumption that had to be reduced in the Port.
KPI30	Power consumption Reduction Periods	Measures the total time when power consumption reduction was performed.
KPI31	Power Curtailed Power	Measures the amount of power that had to be curtailed in the Port.
KPI32	Power Curtailment Periods	Measures the total time when load curtailment was performed.
KPI33	Power consumption Increase	Measures the amount of power consumption that had to be increased in the Port.
KPI34	Power consumption Increase Periods	Measures the total time when power consumption increase was performed.

Besides the above mentioned KPIs, the demo will also consider several “DC specific KPIs”, as defined in deliverable 2.1 (Network Design Tool for DC Solutions). More precisely, the following categories of KPIs will be considered: *i*) efficiency, including total losses in cables, total losses in converters and efficiency ratio; *ii*) environmental, including total weight of components, weight of cables, weight of converters, total lifecycle emissions; and *iii*) economic, including total CAPEX, CAPEX for cables and converters, total OPEX and OPEX for cables and converters.

6.4 Use Cases to be tested

The following section outlines the set of use cases that will be tested within the scope of this demonstrator. For each BUC a general diagram is presented, as well as a table with the respective specialized use cases (SUCs).

6.4.1 BUC1: Port Energy Management

This BUC intends to describe power grid management at the port level, considering OPS and interactions with the system operator (SO). In the present BUC, only the normal operation of the port

is described, excluding services to the grid, the possibility of operating as a microgrid, or utilizing other energy carriers like hydrogen. An overview of this BUC is provided in Figure 6.7.

Figure 6.7: Flowchart representation of DC Port Digital Twin BUC1 – Power Energy Management / Onshore Power Supply.

6.4.2 BUC2: Port/Grid Coordination

This BUC intends to describe the activation of different services by the SO, which will require port-grid coordination. The services can be used to solve the system and/or grid services. The main aim is not to understand why the services are activated, nor how the grid-port coordination is achieved. Instead, the goal is to assess how the port – through the shore side operator (SSO) – can participate in these services. An overview of the services that will be considered in this BUC is presented in Figure 6.8.

Figure 6.8: Flowchart representation of DC Port Digital Twin BUC2 – Port/Grid Coordination

6.4.3 BUC3: Port Microgrid

This BUC intends to describe the activation of Microgrid Operation. Microgrid operation can be activated in different cases, depending on the triggering event(s) and the entity that activates the service, i.e., the SO or the SSO. An illustration of this BUC is provided in Figure 6.9.

Figure 6.9: Flowchart representation of DC Port Digital Twin BUC3 – Port Microgrid

6.4.4 BUC4: Port Energy Hub

This use case describes DC port operation with on-site hydrogen generation and storage, or the possibility of acquiring it from the market. To realize this use case several assumptions have to be made: 1) the port can produce H₂ through electrolysis, 2) the port can consume hydrogen to produce electricity through fuel cells, 3) the port can store hydrogen, either from local production or bought from the market, 4) the SSO manages the generation and storage processes; 5) H₂ can be sold and bought to “Hydrogen Stakeholders”; and 6) the price of H₂ (buy and sell) is established daily in markets. An illustration of the decision process for this BUC is provided in Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.10: Flowchart representation of DC Port Digital Twin BUC4 – Port Energy Hub

6.4.5 KPIs per Use Case Scenario

To ensure traceability and relevance of the performance indicators defined in the DC Port Digital Twin demonstrator, it is performed a mapping between the KPIs and the operational scenarios addressed – see Table 6.7 (an “X” indicates that the corresponding KPI is applicable to the given scenario). This Scenario–KPI matrix provides a structured overview of which indicators apply to each scenario, helping to identify where specific measurements are required and supporting targeted analysis for evaluation and decision-making. The matrix also aids in ensuring coverage across technical, operational, and economic dimensions of the port electrification use cases.

Table 6.7: Mapping between project scenarios and associated Key Performance Indicators.

SUC KPI	BUC1						BUC2						BUC3			BUC4		
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3
KPI1		X			X		X											
KPI2		X			X													
KPI3		X			X													
KPI4		X			X													
KPI5					X													
KPI6		X		X	X													
KPI7		X		X	X	X												
KPI8													X	X	X			
KPI9									X									
KPI10							X											
KPI11																X	X	X
KPI12																X	X	X
KPI13	X																	
KPI14		X	X	X														
KPI15		X	X	X														
KPI16		X			X	X	X											
KPI17							X											
KPI18							X											
KPI19							X											
KPI20											X	X						
KPI21											X	X						
KPI22											X	X						
KPI23											X	X						
KPI24																X	X	X
KPI25						X		X										
KPI26								X										
KPI27									X									
KPI28									X									
KPI29											X	X						
KPI30											X	X						
KPI31								X	X				X	X	X			
KPI32								X	X				X	X	X			
KPI33								X	X				X	X	X			
KPI34								X	X				X	X	X			

7 Conclusions

7.1 Summary

Deliverable D4.1 comprehensively defines detailed technical specifications for each demonstrator within the Shift2DC project, outlining essential components, specific configurations, and robust validation methodologies. Clear KPIs ensure thorough assessment and validation, significantly enhancing the credibility and applicability of results.

7.2 Progress

Considerable progress has been achieved in the detailed definition of each demonstrator. Explicit technical descriptions, comprehensive single-line diagrams, preliminary sizing calculations, protective zoning, and defined bills of materials have been completed. This comprehensive approach provides a robust foundation that will facilitate effective implementation, testing, and validation phases.

7.3 Main Challenges

Several specific challenges have been identified during the development of demonstrator specifications:

- **Interoperability:** Ensuring seamless integration of multiple DC components sourced from various manufacturers remains a critical and complex challenge.
- **Protection Mechanisms:** Validating robust and reliable protection schemes, especially in complex DC environments, requires rigorous testing and precise planning.
- **Technical Complexity and Scaling:** Managing technical complexities related to scaling DC solutions and integrating them across various applications demands extensive simulations, iterative testing, and careful optimization.

Addressing these challenges will be crucial to effectively demonstrate the practical and economic viability of DC technologies.

7.4 Next deliverables

Building on the groundwork laid by D4.1, the following deliverables will be critical to the project's subsequent phases:

- **D4.2 Demonstrators' Simulation Results:** This deliverable will document simulation results, providing insights into system optimization and preliminary validations.
- **D4.3 Digital Twin Testing Environment:** Development and detailed evaluation using digital twins, facilitating comprehensive scenario testing and system enhancements.
- **D4.4 Lessons Learned from Demonstrators:** Critical assessment of demonstrator outcomes, identification of key insights, and formulation of recommendations for broader implementation and market adoption.

Together, these deliverables will contribute substantially to refining and promoting innovative medium and low-voltage DC solutions across multiple industry sectors, enhancing both technical understanding and market readiness.

8 References

- [1] European Commission, “Strategic Energy Technology Plan.” 2023.
- [2] El Sayegh, Elsy *et al.*, “D1.4 - Definition and specification of tools, devices, and evaluation KPIs.” 2025.
- [3] Chub, Andrii, “D1.3 - Use Case Repository.” 2025.
- [4] Current/OS, “The Set of Rules.” Accessed: Mar. 22, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://currentos.foundation/protocol#the-set-of-rules>
- [5] International Maritime Organization, “2023 IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships,” 2023 IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships. Accessed: Apr. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Environment/Pages/2023-IMO-Strategy-on-Reduction-of-GHG-Emissions-from-Ships.aspx>
- [6] N. N. Abu Bakar, N. Bazmohammadi, J. C. Vasquez, and J. M. Guerrero, “Electrification of onshore power systems in maritime transportation towards decarbonization of ports: A review of the cold ironing technology,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 178, p. 113243, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2023.113243.
- [7] K. Kim, K. Park, G. Roh, and K. Chun, “DC-grid system for ships: a study of benefits and technical considerations,” *J. Int. Marit. Saf. Environ. Aff. Shipp.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1080/25725084.2018.1490239.

APPENDIX A: Building Demo – Detailed single-line diagrams

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